

Computational study on imidazole-2-carboxaldehyde-glycylglycine and indole-3-carboxaldehyde-glycylglycine Schiff base ligands and equilibrium studies on their metal complexes

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Abstract : Semiempirical (AM1) calculations were carried out for the Schiff bases, imidazole-2-carboxaldehyde-glycylglycine (imal-glygly) and indole-3-carboxaldehyde-glycylglycine (indal-glygly). Five conformers of imal-glygly and indal-glygly suitable for complex formation were studied. The stable conformers were chosen for further studies. The geometrical parameters are in good agreement with the experimental values. The Schiff bases are planar with C_1 symmetry. The denticity reduction energy for imal-glygly and indal-glygly are respectively 21.04 kcal/mol and 18.24 kcal/mol. imal-glygly is a potentially tetradentate ligand capable of binding through N_4 , N_7 , N_{11}/O_{10} and O_{15} and indal-glygly is tridentate using N_{11} , N_{15}/O_{14} and O_{15} atoms. The basicity of the hetero atoms were studied by calculating the protonation constant. The higher dipole moment values indicate that they are highly soluble in polar solvents. The ionization potential is 11.70 eV and 8.59 eV respectively for imal-glygly and indal-glygly. The chemical hardness has also been studied. Equilibrium studies were carried out for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -imal-glygly/indal-glygly systems. $M(AB)$ and $M(AB)_2$ types of complexes were formed for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} systems, while Cu^{II} forms only $M(AB)$. The stability of the metal ions follows Irving-Williams order.

Keywords : Computation, equilibrium, Schiff base, imidazole-2-carboxaldehyde, indole-3-carboxaldehyde, potentiometry.

Introduction

Schiff bases and their metal complexes are having extensive applications in the field of chemistry and biology¹⁻⁴. Solution chemistry has its own merits in the field of science. The strong polar topology of the Schiff bases lead to compute their molecular features using computational methods. Due to the recent advancement in the quantum chemical methodology, an accurate description about molecular properties such as conformation⁵, structure⁶, vibration⁷ and electronic properties⁸ are possible. In order to fulfill these objectives and in continuation of our earlier reports⁹⁻¹² on Schiff base metal complexes, the present paper reports the computational study on two Schiff bases viz. imidazole-2-carboxaldehyde-glycylglycine (imal-glygly) and indole-3-carboxaldehyde-glycylglycine (indal-glygly) and the equilibrium studies on Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -imal-glygly and indal-glygly complex systems.

Results and discussion

Computational study :

imal-glygly :

Conformational study :

Five conformers suitable for complex formation were chosen. The structure, numbering pattern, total energy, band gap and symmetry of the conformers are given in Fig. 1. Except conformer 3 all others are having C_s symmetry. The total energy (Fig. 1) shows that the stability of the conformers is in the order : 1 > 2 > 3 > 4 > 5. The chemical hardness¹³ calculated from the band gap values (Fig. 1) follows the order : 5 > 4 > 3 > 2 > 1. For further studies conformer 1 is taken.

Geometry :

The important geometrical parameters are given in Table 1. The geometrical parameters are in good agreement with the experimental values^{14,15}. Based on dihedral angles, the molecule can be predicted to be planar.

Conformer 1

TE = -2545.24 kcal/mol- C_s

BG = 9.33 eV

Conformer 2

TE = -2540.96 kcal/mol- C_s

BG = 9.74 eV

Conformer 3

TE = -2522.13 kcal/mol- C_s

BG = 9.88 eV

Conformer 4

TE = -2522.08 kcal/mol- C_s

BG = 10.09 eV

Conformer 5

TE = -2511.97 kcal/mol- C_s

BG = 10.21 eV

Fig. 1. Structure, numbering pattern, total energy (TE), band gap (BG) and symmetry of the conformers of Schiff base ligand imal-glygly.

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of imal-glygly and indal-glygly

indal-glygly		imal-glygly	
Atom pair		Atom pair	
Bond length (Å)			
C ₆ -N ₇	1.3199	C ₁₀ -N ₁₁	1.3199
C ₉ -N ₁₁	1.3199	C ₁₃ -N ₁₅	1.3199
N ₁₁ -C ₁₂	1.4700	N ₁₅ -C ₁₆	1.4699
C ₁₃ -O ₁₅	1.3599	C ₁₇ -O ₁₉	1.3600
Bond angle (A°)			
C ₅ -C ₆ -N ₇	119.9999	C ₇ -C ₁₀ -N ₁₁	119.9999
C ₈ -C ₉ -O ₁₀	119.9999	C ₁₂ -C ₁₀ -C ₁₀	120.0000
N ₁₁ -C ₁₂ -C ₁₃	109.4709	N ₁₅ -C ₁₃ -C ₁₂	120.0000
O ₁₄ -C ₁₃ -O ₁₅	120.0000	C ₁₇ -N ₁₅ -C ₁₃	109.4710
Dihedral (°)			
N ₁ -C ₂ -C ₃ -N ₄	180.000	N ₁₁ -C ₁ -C ₇ -C ₆	0.157000
C ₈ -N ₇ -C ₆ -C ₅	180.000	C ₁₂ -C ₁₀ -C ₁₀ -C ₈	179.9337
C ₉ -C ₈ -N ₇ -C ₆	179.999	C ₁₃ -N ₁₁ -N ₁₁ -C ₇	180.0000
O ₁₀ -C ₉ -C ₈ -N ₇	179.999	O ₁₄ -C ₁₂ -C ₁₂ -C ₁₀	180.0000
N ₁₁ -C ₉ -C ₈ -N ₇	179.999	N ₁₅ -C ₁₃ -C ₁₂ -N ₁₁	180.0001
O ₁₄ -C ₁₃ -C ₁₂ -N ₁₁	179.999	O ₁₈ -C ₁₆ -N ₁₅ -N ₁₁	179.9999
O ₁₅ -C ₁₃ -C ₁₂ -N ₁₁	179.999	O ₁₉ -C ₁₇ -C ₁₆ -C ₁₄	179.9999

This is due to the *sp*² hybridization of carbon and nitrogen atoms of the molecule. The density reduction energy due to the formation of Schiff base between imidazole-2-carboxaldehyde (imal) and glycylglycine (glygly) is 21.04 kcal/mol.

The Mulliken atomic charge density values (Table 2) show the possible donor atoms in imal-glygly to be : N₄,

Table 2. Mulliken atomic charge density

imal-glygly		indal-glygly	
Atom	Charge density	Atom	Charge density
N ₁	-0.1348	N ₉	-0.2046
N ₄	-0.1043	N ₁₁	-0.2191
N ₇	-0.1786	O ₁₄	-0.3882
N ₁₁	-0.3655	N ₁₅	-0.3685
O ₁₄	-0.3590	O ₁₈	-0.3549
O ₁₈	-0.3127	O ₁₉	-0.3199

N₇, N₁₁ or O₁₀ and O₁₅ and it can function as a potentially tetradentate ligand. The dipolemoment of imal-glygly is 8.75 D indicating it is highly soluble in polar solvents. Further, Mulliken atomic orbital electron population (Table 3) shows that both N₇ and N₁₁ can coordinate through *p_z* orbital and N₄ and O₁₅ coordinate through *p_y* orbital. It has fourty filled orbitals with the ionization potential value of 11.70 eV. The band gap value is 9.33

Table 3. Mulliken orbital electron population

imal-glygly		indal-glygly	
Atomic orbital	Electron population	Atomic orbital	Electron population
sN ₄	0.00002	sN ₁₁	0.00013
<i>p_x</i> N ₄	0.00002	<i>p_x</i> N ₁₁	0.00047
<i>p_y</i> N ₄	0.00001	<i>p_y</i> N ₁₁	-0.00011
<i>p_z</i> N ₄	-0.06736	<i>p_z</i> N ₁₁	-0.3576
sN ₇	-0.00002	sN ₁₅	0.00004
<i>p_x</i> N ₇	-0.00001	<i>p_x</i> N ₁₅	0.00059
<i>p_y</i> N ₇	-0.00002	<i>p_y</i> N ₁₅	-0.00071
<i>p_z</i> N ₇	-0.21609	<i>p_z</i> N ₁₅	-0.28255
sN ₁₁	-0.00001	sO ₁₉	0.00001
<i>p_x</i> N ₁₁	0.00044	<i>p_x</i> O ₁₉	0.00011
<i>p_y</i> N ₁₁	0.00002	<i>p_y</i> O ₁₉	-0.00023
<i>p_z</i> N ₁₁	-0.34838	<i>p_z</i> O ₁₉	-0.02001
sO ₁₅	0.00001		
<i>p_x</i> O ₁₅	0.00000		
<i>p_y</i> O ₁₅	-0.00017		
<i>p_z</i> O ₁₅	-0.03133		

eV. Based on ionization potential and band gap, it can be concluded that imal-glygly is a stable molecule.

Basicity :

imal-glygly has four hetero atoms viz. N₁, N₇, N₁₁ and O₁₅ suitable for coordination with metal ions. In order to find out the donor strength of these atoms the protonation energies were calculated and tabulated in Table 4. Among the hetero atoms O₁₅ has an acidic proton and it is exempted for the basicity calculation. All the

Table 4. Protonation energy

imal-glygly			indal-glygly		
Atom	Energy (kcal/mol)	Symmetry	Atom	Energy (kcal/mol)	Symmetry
N ₁	-2420.94	C _s	N ₁₁	-3289.65	C _s
N ₇	-2398.03	C _s	O ₁₄	-3272.27	C ₁
N ₁₁	-2428.55	C _s	N ₁₅	-3312.03	C _s
O ₁₀	-2419.47	C _s			

protonated structures have C_s symmetry. The protonation energy is of the order : N₁₁ > N₁ > O₁₀ > N₇. This shows that the peptide nitrogen is having higher binding ability compared to other atoms.

indal-glygly :

Conformational study :

Five conformers suitable for complex formation for

indal-glygly were chosen for the study. The structure, numbering pattern, total energy and symmetry of the conformers are given in Fig. 2. All the conformers are having C_s symmetry. The total energy of the conformers

shows their stability to be in the order : 1 > 4 > 2 > 3 > 5. The chemical hardness (Fig. 2) is of the order : 5 > 3 > 2 > 4 > 1. All the conformers are planar in structure. Conformer 1 is considered for further study.

Fig. 2. Structure, numbering pattern, total energy (TE), band gap (BG) and symmetry of conformers of indal-glygly.

Geometry :

The important geometrical parameters are given in Table 1. The denticity reduction energy calculated is 18.24 kcal/mol. This is less than that of imal-glygly. Mulliken atomic charge density (Table 2) shows that it is a potentially tridentate ligand binding through azomethine nitrogen (N_{11}), peptide nitrogen (N_{15}) or peptide oxygen (O_{14}) and carboxylato oxygen (O_{19}) atoms. Further, the electron density of indal-glygly is higher than that of imal-glygly. Thus, imal-glygly is comparatively more stable than indal-glygly due to resonance stabilization. This is also confirmed by the denticity reduction energy. N_{11} and O_{19} atoms can bind through p_z orbital and the N_{15} bonds through p_y orbital (Table 3).

The dipolemoment value is 7.10 D. This higher value indicates its high solubility in polar solvents. The Mulliken atomic orbital electron population shows that N_{11} , N_{15} and O_{19} have similar binding behaviour with the metal ions. The ionization potential and band gap values are respectively 8.59 eV and 8.87 eV. Thus, indal-glygly is a stable molecule.

Basicity :

In order to know the potential of the binding atoms, their basicities were calculated from protonation energy. The indal-glygly has three hetero atoms N_{11} , O_{14} and N_{15} . All the protonated structures have C_s symmetry, while protonation at O_{14} has C_1 symmetry. The basicity is of the order : $N_{15} > N_{11} > O_{14}$. This shows that nitrogens are having higher potential for protonation compared to oxygen.

Equilibrium studies :

Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -imal-glygly complex systems :

The log β_{HAB} value of 3.52 for imal-glygly agree well with that for similar Schiff base ligand systems¹⁶. The mono protonated form of the Schiff base is more stable and is predominant in aqueous solution. The pro-

ton in HAB is bound to the azomethine nitrogen and is stabilized through intramolecular hydrogen bonding interaction¹⁷.

The stability constant values of the complexes are given in Table 5. The log β_{CoAB} value is 11.82 indicating the tetradentate binding of imal-glygly. Further, Mulliken atomic charge density of imal-glygly confirms that imal-glygly is a tetradentate ligand. The log $\beta_{Co(AB)_2}$ value is 16.54. If both the Schiff base ligands (AB) bind in a tetradentate mode in $Co(AB)_2$ species, the coordination number of the metal ion becomes eight, which is not possible for 3d metal ions, in general. Therefore each Schiff base (AB) ligand can bind in a tridentate mode, or one ligand can bind in a tetradentate mode and other can bind in a bidentate mode.

The log β value of $Ni(AB)$ is 12.38, while that for $Ni(AB)_2$ is 17.89. The ligand imal-glygly can be tetradentate in $Ni(AB)$. In $Ni(AB)_2$ similar mode of binding as that in Co^{II} -imal-glygly system can be expected. Copper forms only $CuAB$ species. The log β_{CuAB} value is 18.81, indicating the tetradentate binding of the ligand.

$Zn(AB)$ and $Zn(AB)_2$ species were found to be present in zinc-imal-glygly system. The stability constant values for $Zn(AB)$ and $Zn(AB)_2$ complexes are respectively 11.58 and 16.42 log units. As in the other systems, in $Zn(AB)$ the ligand would be tetradentate and in $Zn(AB)_2$ both the ligands can be tridentate or one ligand can be tetradentate and other ligand would be bidentate. The stability of the complexes follows Irving-Williams order : $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$. The $M(AB)$ complex was found to have a maximum concentration of 65–75% of the total metal ion in the pH range of 6–7 in the 1 : 1 solution, while $M(AB)_2$ is predominant in 1 : 2 solution in higher pH.

Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -indal-glygly complex systems :

As in the case of imal-glygly, the monoprotonated

Table 5. Stability constant of metal-Schiff base complexes

System	imal-glygly			indal-glygly		
	log β_{HAB}	log β_{MAB}	log $\beta_{M(AB)_2}$	log β_{HAB}	log β_{MAB}	log $\beta_{M(AB)_2}$
Protonation	3.52	-	-	3.64	-	-
Co^{II}	-	11.82	16.54	-	10.24	15.45
Ni^{II}	-	12.38	17.89	-	11.11	16.32
Cu^{II}	-	18.81	-	-	17.41	-
Zn^{II}	-	11.58	16.42	-	10.38	15.52

form of the Schiff base indal-glygly is more stable with the $\log \beta_{\text{HAB}}$ value of 3.64. The proton in HAB is bound to the azomethine nitrogen and is stabilized by the hydrogen bonding interaction with carboxylato group¹⁷. Co(AB) and Co(AB)₂ complexes were detected in this system in addition to HAB species. The $\log \beta_{\text{CoAB}}$ is 10.24 log units. This value indicates that indal-glygly is tridentate. Mulliken atomic charge density calculations also demonstrate the tridentate binding of indal-glygly. The $\log \beta_{\text{Co(AB)}_2}$ value is 15.45 and in the Co(AB)₂ species, both the Schiff base ligands can function as tridentate giving a coordination number of six to the metal ion.

Ni(AB) and Ni(AB)₂ species were detected in Ni^{II}-indal-glygly system and the $\log \beta$ values are respectively 11.11 and 16.32. Like Co^{II} system, indal-glygly can serve as a tridentate ligand in both Ni(AB) and Ni(AB)₂ complexes. In copper system only Cu(AB) species was detected. The stability constant value of 17.41 log units for Cu(AB) indicates indal-glygly to bind in a tridentate mode. The Schiff base complexes Zn(AB) and Zn(AB)₂ are detected in zinc(II) system. The stability constant values obtained for Zn(AB) and Zn(AB)₂ complexes are respectively 10.38 and 15.52 log units. In both the complexes the ligand indal-glygly can serve as tridentate ligand. The stability of the complexes follows Irving-Williams order. In all the systems, M(AB) complex is found to have a maximum concentration in the 1 : 1 solution and M(AB)₂ complexes are preferred above pH 7 in the 1 : 2 solution.

Experimental

Semiempirical calculations were carried out using MOPAC 6 program¹⁸. All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The stability constants were evaluated potentiometrically at 25 ± 0.1 °C and ionic strength of $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The stability constants were calculated using the computer programme BEST¹⁹. All the calculations have been restricted to systems at $\text{pH} < 8$.

Conclusion :

Both the the Schiff base ligands imal-glygly and indal-glygly are planar with C₁ symmetry. imal-glygly is po-

tentially tetradentate and indal-glygly is tridentate. Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}-imal-glygly and indal-glygly systems form M(AB) and M(AB)₂ complexes, while the Cu^{II} systems form only M(AB) species.

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